

Education and Culture DG

Lifelong Learning Programme

Leonardo da Vinci

Digital Curator Vocational Education Europe DigCurV

**Deliverable 1.1: Report of Kick-off meeting and
action plan, London, 17-18 January 2011**

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Meeting Report

A two-day kick-off meeting was held in London on 17th and 18th February 2011. The aim of the meeting was to:

- brief participants on the project concepts, work plan, financial and reporting provisions etc;
- to gather preliminary information on backgrounds, trends and initiatives concerning the delivery of vocational training in digital curation;
- to gather information on the status of vocational training from several countries; and to ascertain the state of the art in curriculum development

The meeting was attended by a representative of each partner together with a representative of a stakeholder from each country. The full agenda for the meeting is appended as Annex 1 and the list of participants forms Annex 2.

Administration and Financial Management

Kate Fernie (MDR), DigCurV project manager, began by giving partners an overview of the project workplan, the administration arrangements, reporting and financial management responsibilities. Dates for forthcoming project meetings were discussed.

The meeting was then joined by the stakeholders and the remainder of the day focused on presentations covering the context for the project and vocational education and training in digital curation.

Figure 1: Participants at the DigCurV kickoff meeting

Project Overview

Kate Fernie (MDR), began by giving an overview of the EU context in which the i2010 initiative and now the Digital Agenda for Europe has seen a strong and continuing growth in the volumes of digital content being created and received by cultural institutions. Developments in ICT have created unbelievable opportunities¹ for access coupled with challenges for digital preservation and new management responsibilities for Europe's 50,000 cultural institutions². While professional training in the care of traditional collections is well established for archivists, librarians and museum curators, training in the long term management of digital collections has been identified as a major issue³. Institutions are facing difficulties in recruiting staff with skills in the field of digital curation, at the same time there is demand from staff for training to develop the new skills needed. Digital curation and preservation are recognised to be rapidly evolving fields; to perform effectively, staff working in these fields will need to be able to update their knowledge and skills on a continuous basis⁴. But this is set against a context where the existing training offer consists largely of short courses provided by competence centres or projects on specific topics.

The DigCurV project aims to address the availability of vocational education and training needed by curators in the library, archive, museum and cultural heritage sectors to develop the new skills that are essential for the long-term management of digital collections. With funding from the Leonardo da Vinci programme, this thirty-month project will identify, analyse and profile existing training opportunities, survey training needs in the sector to identify the key skills and competences required of digital curators. DigCurV aims to establish a curriculum framework from which training can be developed in future. The curriculum will be tested and evaluated by stakeholders during the project.

[View presentation](#)

Digital Curation and Lifelong Learning: a brief overview of EU initiatives and projects

Ann Gow (University of Glasgow) gave a brief introduction to previous EU funded projects which have been active in the field of digital preservation including:

- PLANETS, <http://www.planets-project.eu/>
- Digital Preservation Europe (DPE), <http://www.digitalpreservationeurope.eu/>
- CASPAR, <http://www.casparpreserves.eu/>
- DELOS, <http://www.delos.info/>
- SHAMAN, <http://shaman-ip.eu/shaman/>
- ERPANET, <http://www.erpanet.org/>

¹ The New Renaissance: report of the Comité des Sages.
http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/activities/digital_libraries/doc/refgroup/final_report_cds.pdf

² NUMERIC report, 2009
http://www.cipfastats.net/default_view.asp?content_ref=9743

³ DPC training needs report, 2004 http://www.jisc.ac.uk/uploaded_documents/finalReport.pdf

⁴ Digital Preservation Europe, Briefing paper on Professional Development.
http://www.digitalpreservationeurope.eu/publications/professional_development.pdf

Each of these projects organised training events which were often attached to major conferences or to other events. It is worth noting that the training delivered by these projects reflected the project focus on a specific technology or sector.

A number of new projects and initiatives are starting in 2011 including:

- APARSEN (the Alliance on Permanent Access to the Records of Science in Europe Network, <http://www.alliancepermanentaccess.org/>),
- Timbus (Digital Preservation for Timeless Business Processes and Services)
- SCAPE (Scaleable Preservation Environments) and
- The Open Planets Foundation, which has been set up to build on the research results of PLANETS to provide practical solutions and expertise, and has a mandate for training.

Ann Gow concluded by talking about the lessons learned, noting that while some of the training which has been developed is generic and goes across boundaries there are discipline related issues which need to be taken into account.

[View presentation](#)

Life Long Learning Programme, projects and initiatives in adult learning

Rob Davies (MDR) began by showing a short video giving an overview of the Lifelong Learning programme (LLP), which is the flagship European Union funding programme in the field of education and training. LLP is divided in four sub programmes which each focussing on different on different stages:

- Comenius for schools
- Erasmus for higher education
- Leonardo da Vinci for vocational education and training
- Grundtvig for adult education

The DigCurV project has been funded under the Leonardo da Vinci sub programme, which focuses on vocational education and training (other than at higher education level). The programme aims to address all of the parties involved including trainees in vocational education, teachers and trainers, institutions and educational bodies, enterprises, associations, social partners and employers.

[View Lifelong Learning Programme video](#)

[View Leonardo da Vinci programme video](#)

Innovation in adult learning

Seamus Ross (University of Toronto) began by noting that in comparison to other professions the cultural heritage has no current requirement for the number of hours of education its staff should engage in each year. He remarked that the Leonardo da Vinci video that the group had just watch had presented professional development from the perspective of an individual; the focus was on what individuals need to do to ensure they have new skills to stay relevant in the marketplace.

The cultural heritage domain has not really defined what is needed to stay relevant and it has tended to look inwards. Other domains have taken a different approach. For example Google has been digitising content from the cultural heritage domain but looked at the methodologies used in other industries such as banking for managing the process to maintain the authenticity of the material while digitising at speed.

For DigCurV to be successful it needs to put in place programmes which are relevant to the cultural heritage domain and also recognised by that community. It will be important to build up the network and to get libraries, museums and archives and professional associations to engage in the project and then to recognise curriculum that is developed. This will really add credibility to it in Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programmes.

Seamus Ross went on to discuss the importance to professionals of accreditation and certification of vocational education and training. Certificates are valued where policies and procedures for quality assurance are seen to be in place, while good assessment mechanisms measure the effectiveness of a curriculum and the learning obtained. Accreditation of a curriculum by a professional body improves its impact and effectiveness within the profession.

There are very few accredited courses covering digital curation within the cultural heritage domain at the moment. The UK Society of Archivists is an exception and is accrediting courses which cover aspects of digital preservation and digital curation for archivists.

It is worth looking at examples from other fields. PRINCE, a project management methodology developed in the UK, training is delivered at different centres to the same standards and participants obtain certificates recognised by employers as a consistent measure (<http://www.prince2.com/>). The European Computer Driving Licence (ECDL), the international computer skills certification programme, is another good example of a standard framework for structured training and certificates which people can take in different countries and obtain a standard qualification <http://www.ecdl.com/>.

Seamus Ross concluded by discussing his vision of the DigCurV curriculum as a framework for continuing professional development which can be implemented by different accredited institutions. There may be potential to develop a franchise model to support accreditation and continue development of the curriculum.

Training needs: the employers' perspective

Joyce Ray (IMLS) spoke about the employers' perspective on education and training for digital curators based on experience in the USA. She reported that the American Library Association annual placement and salary survey⁵ for 2010 showed a general decline in available positions with the only growth areas being archives, digital

⁵ Placement and Salaries Survey 2009, The Library Journal
<http://www.libraryjournal.com/article/CA6699218.html>

repositories and scholarly communications. The survey reported new job titles are being filled by graduates of information science programmes using their technology, metadata and database skills with average salaries which are quite a bit higher than for traditional jobs. This is definitely a growth area.

Employers have a role to play in defining these new jobs and the skills needed to get staff up to speed on; they need to recognise that staff will require more training than can be offered in a couple of workshops and make an institutional commitment.

There is great demand on the practitioner side, from staff working currently in Libraries, Archives and Museums who feel they don't have the skills needed today. For example, a session on archival education organised by the Society of American Archivists last summer was very well attended. People were saying: 'I can't get the knowledge I need at my institution'.

DigCurV will need to determine at what level its curriculum will be and how this relates to other programmes. There are different levels being offered at the moment. For example:

- the University of Arizona has an online certificate programme in Digital Curation which is being taken by people with BA degrees and by people in employment with Masters degrees.
- John Hopkins University has an online Museum Studies masters' degree programme with a technology focus that is attracting both museum professionals already working in museums as well as students who aspire to professional museum jobs; this programme includes a course in digital preservation as of 2011. Commitment from the employing institution is important as students gain more from education and training if they go back to institutions with the capacity and services needed for digital curation, such as institutional repositories.

An example of a library which has done work in this area is Purdue University Library, which established a Distributed Data Curation Centre (D2C2)⁶ and is developing services. It has created digital curation profiles and a toolkit for investigating the information practices and needs of researchers working in different disciplines. The centre is now developing a series of workshops relating to digital curation based on the toolkit. A workshop on digital curation profiles offered as a pre-conference to the 2011 IMLS Webwise Conference reached capacity at nearly 200 registrants a month before the conference.

Joyce Ray noted the importance of raising awareness about digital preservation amongst cultural institutions. She reported that the US Library of Congress had conducted a survey of directors of small to medium sized cultural heritage organisations and found that they saw digital preservation as being very important and were willing learn about it. But she noted that there is a perception that the training requirement is simple; a majority of respondents said they could devote no

⁶ Purdue University, D2C3: <http://d2c2.lib.purdue.edu/>

more than a half-day to one day to a training class. There is a need to raise awareness of what is required to do digital preservation.

The sector is seeing the emergence of services, which benefits the institutions who were previously having to work independently and build their own systems from scratch. An example of a new service in the US is Duracloud, a mass storage service which is being rolled out by Duraspace (which was formed as a merger of DSpace and FEDORA). There may be roles for other service providers or mediators for smaller institutions who don't have capacity to do digital preservation by themselves and who need help in making effective use of services such as Duracloud. The Open Planets Foundation in Europe is another model for how those services can be deployed.

DigCurV should take these developments into account; the curriculum might for example show what services are available for exploitation by institutions.

Seamus Ross suggested looking at developments in other areas while thinking about DigCurV. Joyce Ray noted that scientific data is huge. The recent Riding the Wave report⁷ draws attention to how Europe can use scientific data to boost its economy and highlights the importance of preservation and curation of the data.

There has been an assumption that academic disciplines will manage research data or their disciplines. But surveys have shown that there are not many disciplinary repositories and those that exist often take only datasets. Therefore, researchers are managing their data, particularly raw data, themselves. This puts the burden on the university and is at present uncoordinated and undocumented. Now that the US National Science Foundation and other federal agencies such as IMLS are requiring grant applicants to submit data management plans with applications for research grants, researchers at institutions that have institutional repositories will be advantaged in grant competitions. This creates huge opportunities for the development of institutional repositories, but institutions need to develop human capacity as well as the technical infrastructure to manage this data. Libraries and archives can play an important role in developing data management services, in cooperation with disciplinary researchers and ICT services, but they need to get up to speed quickly.

Joyce Ray concluded by reporting that the IMLS has a programme on training and education in library and information science which includes both formal education and continuing education. The initial aim of the programme was to increase the numbers of students graduating to fill posts left vacant by librarians retiring. But the current evidence is that jobs are shifting and IMLS is now looking at the skills and knowledge needed by today's information professionals more broadly. With the increasing dependence of the knowledge environment on information technology, the requirements for librarians and archivists is converging in many ways. Digital curation is the bridge that brings them together. The role of digital curation in managing information, such as scientific databases, so that it is interoperable across

⁷ Riding the Wave – how Europe can benefit from the rising tide of scientific data, Final report of the high level expert group on scientific data, 2010:

http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/cf/document.cfm?action=display&doc_id=707

disciplines and can be found and used by others beyond its original purposes creates opportunities for those in the LIS workforce with skills in digital curation to take up new jobs in this field.

Training and learning modes: student experiences

Susan Schreibman (Trinity College, Dublin) began by speaking about the 'Laws of Learning' which relate to DigCurV:

- the law of readiness: people won't learn until they really need to. In the case of digital curation, people are ready to learn;
- the law of simplicity: it is important to avoid people from getting overwhelmed by the acronyms, standards and technology; and
- the law of involvement: the more that people do things, the more they remember.

Susan Schreibman went on to discuss differences between training and learning, and the different reasons students have for taking courses. It is important to provide students with opportunities to reinforce their learning at home through materials and exercises. In some cases people take courses to prepare for work that they themselves will be doing, while others take the same course to prepare to supervise the work of others. It is important to know the profile of students.

Short training courses are good for introducing new tools, methods and high level concepts etc. Some organisations spend a lot sending staff on short courses.

There are various modes of education used for course delivery including:

- face to face learning
- web based synchronous learning (a group of people online at the same time interacting with each other in real time)
- web based asynchronous (student centred learning using online resources to share information with others through email, discussion boards and other means)
- blended learning – a mixture of the above learning environments.

A study of continuing education for librarians carried out by the State of Tennessee found that 86% of respondents preferred face to face learning. This was a surprise result which could reflect a number of factors (local, previous experience, etc), which may not be relevant to the context of DigCurV. There are known difficulties in conveying personality through remote learning and in encouraging interaction. Technical skills are difficult to teach through distance education – but scenarios are changing with the emergence of new techniques such as screen sharing and new tools.

Susan Schreibman went on to discuss the current trend for student centred learning, which is set in a context in technical disciplines like digital curation where students show signs of preferring their teacher to dispense knowledge, rather than learning from other students. She suggested that students want to hear how to do things ('the right answer') and are less interested in theory. Other educators in the group

agreed, remarking that for many students anything that is not hands on at the moment is theory. Educators want to give students enough theory so they can move on to the next technology.

DigCurV's target audience is people with prior knowledge. One educational approach is to work with the prior knowledge to get people to make a conceptual shift and apply their knowledge in a different area; for example, applying knowledge of curation of physical objects to the digital field. But there can be barriers to learning - if something doesn't fit into someone's world picture it can be difficult to learn.

In conclusion there was a discussion amongst the participants at the meeting about the development of online learning and the possible implications for DigCurV.

Vision for DigCurV project: working towards a curriculum framework for digital curation

During the meeting there was a whole group discussion about the DigCurV project and its vision of working towards a curriculum framework for digital curation. A range of issues were discussed including:

The contexts in which the curriculum will be delivered:

- domains (archives, libraries, museums)
- national circumstances, e.g. national legislation and language
- institutional stages:
 - setting up digital curation systems
 - running digital curation systems
- people at different levels and stages:
 - Policy makers
 - Managers/employers
 - Staff
- Skill sets:
 - Technical
 - Managerial
 - Policy

The group recognised a need for a basic training and education curricula in every country to raise awareness of digital curation amongst employers and staff. This should take into account that cultural institutions collect digital data to provide user services.

The group vision for the DigCurV curriculum is of a framework for core concepts and methods which are applicable in the different contexts. It will define types of people, sectors (museums, libraries, archives) and skills/competences relevant to the lifecycle of digital objects, and will provide a scaffold or model from which specific courses can be developed.

The opportunity is to show that the DigCurV curriculum is transferable to different countries and sectors.

Exploitation of the curriculum

The group recognised a demand from staff and employers for CPD courses to be certified, and for the qualifications obtained to be recognised, transparent and portable. Amongst the educators represented in the group there is a demand for a curriculum from which to develop courses in digital curation, and potential demand from other training centres. During the day there was discussion about what this meant both in terms of testing of the knowledge and skills acquired by students, and accreditation of training centres delivering the DigCurV curriculum. Models for exploitation of the curriculum will be investigated during the project.

Key developments in participating countries

One of the objectives of the kickoff meeting was to gather information about the status of vocational education and training and curriculum development in the participating countries. Representatives from each country shared their national experience revealing wide differences in advancement:

Germany, Austria and Switzerland: the nestor consortium

Stefan Strathmann (University of Goettingen) and Achim Oßwald (University of Cologne) spoke about the nestor initiative in Germany, Austria and the German speaking areas of Switzerland.

nestor is voluntary initiative and cooperation between organisations in the museum, libraries and archives sector. The nestor qualification group of universities has a memorandum of understanding to inform their work together, which has the long term objective is establishing a cooperative and distributed degree in digital curation. Over the last 3 years the qualifications group has organised seminars and summer schools, has produced the nestor handbook on digital curation (to raise awareness by making information available in German), and prepared an elearning tutorial.

The nestor schools are one-week courses in a remote location – the tutors and students are resident for the week to intensify the experience. Participants receive a certificates and are awarded credits in the European Credit Transfer system⁸, which can be used in conjunction with other university courses. The school cover a range of activities and include both practitioners (employees in cultural institutions) and students; the mixture of attitudes and experience, improves the course. Students have developed a number of eLearning tutorials under supervision of their professors; 20 tutorials are now available on the moodle platform and available to all the universities that are part of the nestor group, so they can be included in courses.

Until now there has been no digital curation curriculum in Germany or the German speaking area, so nestor has brought university partners together to cooperate which they see as beneficial in this field. As a result of the intense discussions some synergies are emerging. There is also more cross sector cooperation and communication than previously; in the past archivists and librarians felt they had different methods and discussed digital curation separately.

[View presentation](#)

⁸ European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS)
http://ec.europa.eu/education/lifelong-learning-policy/doc48_en.htm

Ireland

Susan Schreibman (Trinity College Dublin) and Annette Kelly (Library Council Ireland) spoke about the status of vocational education and training for digital curation in Ireland, noting that little training is currently available and so the DigCurV initiative is really needed. Annette Kelly mentioned that institutions had sent people to the UK for digital preservation courses because of the lack of availability in Ireland, which is currently limited to digitisation and Text Encoding (TEI). Both noted that Irish cultural institutions had come late to digitisation.

Susan Schreibman reported that Trinity College Dublin is planning a Masters degree course in the digital humanities to start in September 2011. She hopes this will also provide an opportunity to create a diploma in digital curation noting there are institutions which would be interested in certifying such a diploma.

Italy

Maurizio Lunghi and Chiara Cirinnà (Fondazione Rinascimento Digitale) described the status of digital curation training in Italy. They noted that cultural repositories have been slow to respond to the need to safeguard digital memories. Public administration and eGovernment responded first with legislation being established 1999-2000. The drivers were:

- the need for public administration records to become more accessible to the people and for business processes to be simplified;
- the law on digital protocol, lead to the development of registration of essential information on incoming and outgoing records.

The Code of Digital Administration law specifies in Article 44 that a person must be appointed to be responsible for the digital preservation of administrative records. But no training is available and nor is there any requirement to participate in training.

The main actors are the:

- Italian ministry of culture which provides courses but not on digital preservation
- Italian Library Association which provides courses but not on digital preservation
- Italian Association of Archivists which is very active on digital preservation and provides courses directed to different levels of staff
- Italian national school of public administration is developing blended learning courses
- Italian section of ICOM (International Council On Museum) which is planning a digital curation course in 2011.

There is a national association for professionals involved in digital preservation, which is a private membership association and is very active in providing short courses to its members. In addition there are private agencies and consultants working to support innovation in the public administration who are developing courses for staff (not limited to those working in public administration). There are some courses available for SMEs.

Chiara Cirinnà gave an overview of higher education in Italy mentioning two consortiums of universities:

- CILEA is a consortium of 10 universities, and is active in providing courses on ICT and electronic publishing and also in digital curation
- UniDOC is a consortium of 20 universities which provide courses on ICT and digital preservation issues.

There are several faculties of archival science and bibliotechnomics in Italy; the main ones providing courses in digital preservation are Urbino, Macerata, Genoa, Pavia and Rome. In addition there are some post graduate schools with specialisation for archivists – with both 1st and 2nd level masters degrees being offered (the difference is the length of the courses and the number of credits obtained).

[View presentation](#)

Italy: Digital Stacks case study

Maurizio Messina (Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana) spoke about the Digital Stacks project as a case study of training requirements. The project is connected with the implementation of Legal Deposit for electronic documents in Italy. Plans to set up a network of legal repositories involving the 2 central national libraries in Florence and Rome, and a number of regional sites were described.

Digital Stacks can be seen as a digital preservation system, as a public service to enable users to access the documents and a service for publishers to help fulfil the obligation of perpetual access to e-journals. The training requirements will be dependent on the service model which is set up. Digital Stacks staff employers will need training to be available in all the issues of digital curation including organisational, technical, legal frameworks (digital rights and copyright management), business models and sustainability models.

There is also a need for training also for publishers to raise awareness about digital curation problems.

[View presentation](#)

Lithuania

Jurate Kupriene (Vilnius University Library) and Irena Kriviene (Lithuanian Academic Libraries Consortium) spoke about the status of digital curation training in Lithuania. They noted that the situation is similar to Ireland. There are no institutions currently offering training in digital curation for librarians, although there is vocational training available for archivists.

Currently there are a lot of people working on cultural sector digitisation projects in Lithuania and some seminars were organised in autumn 2010 by Vilnius University. But there is a need for training in digital preservation, it is quite new.

The Faculty of Communications at Vilnius University prepares librarians and offers programmes covering digitisation issues. The Library has a role to play in talking to colleagues in this faculty to encourage them to include courses on digital

preservation. Last year, Vilnius University Library began to collaborate with a consortium of academic libraries and has received funding from their ministry to establish a repository for the consortium. Some training is planned as part of the work to establish the repository – the institutions need to know what a repository is and how to use it.

In 2012 Vilnius University Library moves into a new building which may present an opportunity to open a training department for cultural heritage institutions on eLibraries covering preservation issues and other aspects of their management.

UK

Joy Davidson (Digital Curation Centre) spoke about a number of other initiatives in which the DCC is involved including:

- 'Digital Curation 101' from the UK, which has been established to provide a one day introduction to digital curation for academic researchers and others on how to manage research data (<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/training/digital-curation-101>).
- 'Closing the Digital Curation Gap', which is an international collaboration between the USA and the UK which aims to integrate best practices, research, development and training in digital curation (<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/projects/closing-digital-curation-gap>).
- The Research Information Network (RIN) in the UK whose information handling group is looking at the development of training in the field for researchers. The Research Data Management Skills Support Initiative (DaMSSI), a collaboration between RIN, the Digital Curation Centre and the JISC, aims to help researchers and their institutions to plan data management skills development and training, and to make recommendations for courses in Library and Information Sciences.

Ann Gow (HATII) talked about a number of other UK initiatives including HATII's own academic programme in information management and museums, which cover digital preservation. She reported that the museums course is newly established as a result of a request from the Kelvingrove museum in Glasgow, which felt there was a lack of training available and staff were joining without the skills needed.

The Digital Preservation Coalition are running road shows across the UK on digital preservation and working very closely with the Digital Curation Centre to provide training for staff in Higher Education Institutions. For example, HATII has started a staff development programme within the University of Glasgow for staff on managing research data.

Other training is being provided in the UK by the JISC (Joint Information Services Committee) and the Collections Trust has started to offer some digital preservation training for staff working in museums and archives.

The Digital Preservation Training Programme (DPTP) offers courses which are sponsored by the Digital Preservation Coalition and the University of London

Computing Centre, and are attended from staff working in cultural institutions <http://www.dptp.org/>.

Canada

Seamus Ross (uToronto) informed the group that the iSchool at the University of Toronto is both a professional and research faculty, which educates leaders in information fields. Study areas focus on the human context of a rapidly changing information environment exploring how information, whether cultural, technological, or archival, interacts with society.

The School offers programmes in Information and Museum Studies, and is home to Canada's largest continuing education program in Information offering courses on information architecture, records management, taxonomies and metadata, and management. It is one of the largest CPD programmes in North America in the field of libraries and information sciences (which includes archives and records management). The University certifies some of its CPD courses, for example in records management. The University of Toronto launched a new Digital Curation Institute in June 2010. In future the School could offer a certificate in Digital Curation based on the results of DigCurV.

USA

Helen Tibbo (University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill) spoke about the status of training in digital curation in the USA. She reported that Chapel Hill has completed 4 projects in digital curation training with IMLS funding:

- DigCCuRR (2006) looked at developing curriculum for masters students. It developed graduate level courses with modules, experience components, international symposiums and a fellowship programme for the masters students. An output was a certificate in digital curation which will sit on top of existing masters degrees offered by the university. A number of resources are available online from the 2009 conference, Digital Curation Practice, Promise and prospects.
- DigCCuRR2 (2008) was funded through IMLS Laura Bush funds to train doctoral students with the aim of creating teaching staff (building the capacity for further training). The US National Archives and University of Toronto are partners in this project which runs to July 2011.
- The Digital Curation Exchange and Summer Institutes emerged from DigCCuRR2. The Summer Institutes are week-long courses - people are sent material ahead of time and remain in touch after the course through the Digital Curation Exchange. Participants have done great projects. After the summer institute participants go back to their institutions and then return in January to report on their experiences in the workplace. This has been a successful model, the January event includes public presentations which are attended by other students. It is hoped this will raise awareness of digital curation.
- Closing the Digital Curation Gap (CDCG) is a joint project between IMLS (Chapel Hill), the JISC and DCC which is looking to establish and support a network of practitioners, researchers and educators through face to face meetings, web based communication, online tools. It aims to establish a baseline of practice – there have been surveys and focus groups with small to

medium sized repositories in the USA and UK. CDCG is developing 5 scenarios relating to running institutional repositories which take people through a decision tree and providing resources with questions and some answers.

- The Sophie project is looking at bringing digital curation to local, county and state governments. One issue which is being looked at by Chapel Hill, the National Archives, Library of Congress, and State Archives is curating social media in permanent public archives.

In terms of continuing education, Chapel Hill offers the Summer Institute (described above). The University of Michigan offers courses which are managerial in focus, being aimed at library directors or people who will run repositories and look at technology, resources and the sociology of the institution. The North East Document Conservation Centre offers some training. The University of Illinois is also developing some training.

Helen Tibbo noted that the sustainability of these courses without IMLS grant funding is an issue, as CPD training is not the core mission of the universities.

Joyce Ray reported that IMLS funding has resulted in the development of a large number of summer institutes and CPD opportunities. The IMLS funding came out of Laura Bush's interest in libraries. The initial vision was to address the problem that librarians are coming up to retirement age and there is a need to recruit a new generation of young librarians. Quite early into the programme IMLS saw that it was less useful to recruit people trained following traditional curriculum and so they created courses 'building institutional capacity' which included digital preservation (around 2006 they began calling it digital curation).

Helen Tibbo concluded by saying that one of the good effects of having programmes of summer institutes is that students see the courses being advertised and it raises awareness of the field. Students are now coming to university saying that they want to do digital stuff.

Action planning

The meeting concluded with a session to plan the project's activities:

Survey of existing training initiatives

Jurate Kupriene (Vilnius University Library) talked about plans to gather information on existing training initiatives, the methodologies, models, topics and resources available. The survey will focus on initiatives in Europe over the last two years. The survey will be made available online and will be disseminated through the partner network and will be open to accept responses from organisations worldwide (it will be designed to allow analysis of the results by country and region).

The group recognises that there is a broader context for education and training in digital curation, which is currently largely delivered by projects, centres of excellence and higher education institutions. Higher education institutions are offering continuing professional development courses alongside their core academic courses in Library and Information Sciences, Archive management and Museum Studies etc. The scope of the survey will include the CPD offer of higher education institutions and other relevant courses.

Review of sector training needs

Stefan Strathmann (University of Goettingen) talked about plans to carry out a review of training needs in the culture sector. The aim is to identify the core competences and key skills needed by managers and staff involved in digital curation, and the review will include an analysis of jobs being advertised and the qualifications requested by employers. The project partners will invite stakeholders to take part in focus groups to contribute information, experience and feedback to the review. An output will be the development of the means of evaluating the DigCurV curriculum framework.

Curriculum framework, design and testing

Ann Gow (HATII) talked about plans to build on the results of the survey of training initiatives and the review of sector training to design the DigCurV curriculum framework. At an early stage the project will review the level of the curriculum and the shape of the framework, and will build this into the initial design. A stakeholder workshop is planned to provide an opportunity to discuss the proposed framework with the community. The feedback from this and other events will help inform the final framework.

Dissemination

The project website has been launched (<http://www.digcur-education.org>) and will provide the platform for disseminating the project's results. A number of other dissemination activities are planned including national focus groups, workshops and other meetings, and dissemination about news and the project's results through Twitter and other social networking channels.

Expanding the Network

DigCurV is a stakeholder network which is open to participation by organisations and individual experts with an interest in training in digital curation for the cultural sector. Members of the network will be invited to share information and to contribute feedback to help to shape and inform the DigCurV curriculum.

Annex 1: DigCurV Kickoff meeting, Agenda

Monday, 17th January

- 10.00 Welcome and introductions
- 10.15 Administration and financial management, Kate Fernie and Carol Usher, MDR
- 10.45 Questions
- 11.00 Break
- 11.20 Introductions
- 11.45 Overview of project objectives, Kate Fernie, MDR Partners
- 12.15 Digital Curation and Lifelong Learning: a brief overview of EU initiatives and projects, Ann Gow, University of Glasgow
- 12.40 Life Long Learning Programme, projects and initiatives in adult learning, Rob Davies, MDR Partners
- 13.00 Lunch
- 14.00 Innovation in adult learning, Seamus Ross, University of Toronto
- 14.30 Training needs: the employers's perspective, Joyce Ray, IMLS
- 15.00 Training and learning modes: student experiences, Susan Schreibman, Trinity College, Dublin
- 15.30 Break
- 16.00 Whole group discussion – our vision for DigCurV project: working towards a curriculum framework for digital curation
- 17.30 Close

Tuesday, 18th January

- 9.00 Key developments in participating countries: tour de table
 Canada, Seamus Ross, University of Toronto
 Germany and Austria: the Nestor Consortium, Stefan Strathmann, University of Goettingen and Achim Oßwald, University of Cologne
 Ireland, Susan Schreibman, Trinity College Dublin and Annette Kelly, Library Council Ireland
 Italy, Maurizio Lunghi and Chiara Cirinnà, Rinascimento Digitale.it with Maurizio Messina
 Lithuania, Jurate Kupriene, Vilnius University and Irena Kriviene, Lithuanian Academic Libraries Consortium
 UK, Joy Davidson, Digital Curation Centre
 USA, Helen Tibbo, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
- 11.00 Break
- 11.30 Action planning
 Whole group discussion about identifying stakeholders and target groups
- 11.45 WP2: Survey of existing training initiatives, Jurate Kupriene
- 12.00 WP3: Review of sector training needs, Stefan Strathmann
- 12.15 WP4: Curriculum framework, design and testing, Ann Gow
- 12.30 WP5: Project website and logo, Carol Usher, MDR Partners
- 12.45 WP5: Dissemination and planning project events, Susan Schreibman
- 13.00 Lunch
- 14.00 Round up and what comes next
- 15.00 Meeting closes

Annex 2: Participants

Name	Organisation	Country
Kate Fernie	MDR Partners	UK
Rob Davies	MDR Partners	UK
Carol Usher	MDR Partners	UK
Joyce Ray	IMLS	USA
Helen Tibbo	Tibbo@email.unc.edu	USA
Seamus Ross	University of Toronto	Canada
Maurizio Lunghi	Fondazione Rinascimento Digitale	Italy
Chiara Cirinnà	Fondazione Rinascimento Digitale	Italy
Maurizio Messina	Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana, Venezia	Italy
Stefan Strathmann	Goettingen State and University Library	Germany
Achim Oßwald	Fachhochschule Köln	Germany
Ann Gow	HATII, University of Glasgow	UK
Joy Davidson	Digital Curation Centre, University of Glasgow	UK
Jurate Kupriene	Vilniaus Universiteto Biblioteka	Lithuania
Irena Kriviene	Vilniaus Universiteto Biblioteka	Lithuania
Susan Schreibman	Trinity College Dublin, Long Room Hub	Ireland
Annette Kelly	Library Council Ireland	Ireland

